

Supporting Information

Linking Composition, Structure and Thickness of CoOOH layers to Oxygen Evolution Reaction Activity by Correlative Microscopy

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Experimental section

Microelectrode fabrication

A glass capillary (100 mm length, outer diameter 1.5 mm, inner diameter 0.86 mm, Science Products GmbH) was cut in the middle (see Figure S1a). One side of each tube was heated to molten states with a butane torch to seal the bottom part, then cobalt wire (99.99+ %, 0.125 mm in diameter, 1.20 cm length, purchased from Goodfellow GmbH) was loaded into it (Figure S1b). Under vacuum condition, the capillary bottom was slowly heated with electrical resistance heater (Figure S1c) until the Co wire sealed by glass. Low melting point alloy (S-Sn₆₀Pb₃₉Cu₁, 0.5 mm diameter, STANNOL GmbH & Co. KG) and Cu conductive wire were loaded from the top of electrode (Figure S1d) and used to weld the exposed Co part (Figure S1e). To protect the electrode, shrinking tube is put on the top of the electrode (Figure S1f).

Grinding and polishing cobalt microelectrode

The microelectrode was first grinded with 4000 grit sandpaper until the microelectrode surface is flat. Then, it was polished with 3 and 1 μm diamond suspensions for 20 minutes each. Finally, the microelectrode was polished with MasterPolish suspension (Buehler Ltd.) for 20 minutes, followed by three times of five-minute ultrasonic cleaning in ethanol.

Electrochemical measurements

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) of 100 cycles (from 0.73 to 1.63 V vs. RHE) was recorded on BioLogic SP-300 potentiostat in 0.1 M KOD (original content 40 wt% in D₂O, Sigma-Aldrich) in D₂O electrolyte (Sigma-Aldrich), with the scan rate 10 mV·s⁻¹. Cobalt microelectrode, Pt wire and Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) serve as the working electrode, counter electrode, and reference electrode, respectively. The current density is normalized to the geometrical surface area and potentials are referred to RHE.

SECCM measurements

SECCM measurements were performed in a dedicated setup exploiting the WEC-SPM Labview control software developed by the Electrochemistry and Interfaces Group at Warwick University. The pipettes were pulled from quartz capillaries (Q120-90-7.5, Sutter Instruments) by means of a P-2000 laser puller (Sutter Instruments). A relatively big opening diameter of around 400 nm was chosen to counteract any blockage of the tip caused by material uptake/redeposition in the tip during cycling on the electrode's surface. After pulling, each pipette was dipped for 30 seconds into dichlorodimethylsilane (thermo scientific, 99%) while applying 7 bar of argon pressure to the back of the pipette to render its outer walls hydrophobic. This procedure was followed by 1 minute of drying under air while keeping the argon pressure. The pipettes were filled with a 10 mM KOH solution (Alfa Aesar, 85% min., metal basis 99.99%), as pH values higher than 12 were avoided not to incur excessive wetting of the electrode surface.

The alignment between the Co microelectrode and the SECCM pipette was inspected via optical microscope, while tip scanning was performed by piezo motors. A 250 μm Pt wire (ChemPUR, 99.9%) was used as the quasi-reference counter electrode (QRCE). The potential of the QRCE was calibrated using 1 mM 1,1'-ferrocene dimethanol (thermo scientific, 98%) as a redox mediator with a known formal potential in 10 mM KOH and performing an SECCM measurement in the hopping CVs mode on a plain glassy carbon electrode over a time span of 90 minutes. The QRCE potential was found to be about 183 mV vs. SHE, drifting by 35 mV per hour into the positive direction. It is assumed that this drift would have led to a time-

dependence in the data discussed in this paper, which was not observed. Therefore, the drift was not compensated for the data evaluation. The electrochemical imaging was performed in a $60 \times 60 \mu\text{m}^2$ area on the as-polished microelectrodes and those after 100 CV cycles, using a $4 \mu\text{m}$ hopping distance between neighboring points. Two CV cycles were performed during each contact to ensure that the footprints were visible enough to relocate the scanned area. The tip was approached applying a voltage of 0.2 V, then performing the two cycles at a scan rate of 0.5 V/s using a lower vertex voltage of 0.2 V and an upper vertex voltage of 0.7 V vs. Pt QRCE. Currents were recorded at a sampling rate of 3000 samples per second with a 1 kHz lowpass Bessel filter, allowing a current less than 1.5 pA peak-to-peak noise level before landing. A current threshold value of 1 pA was selected to trigger the tip to stop the approach, aiming to avoid excessive substrate wetting. The tip approach speed was set to $2.0 \mu\text{m/s}$, and the retraction speed to $4.0 \mu\text{m/s}$ with a retract distance of $7.0 \mu\text{m}$ after each measurement.

Evaluation of the SECCM data was achieved by plotting the current density measured at a fixed potential over the location in the array of the scan. In so doing, maps showing the local changes in activity were created with each pixel representing the current density measured inside an individual droplet cell. The current data was normalized by the footprint area estimated from SEM images. For the pristine sample, a linearly increasing footprint area was assumed due to droplet growth throughout the measurement, and the sizes of the first and last footprint were measured using SEM. Some data points were taken out of the evaluation because the data and footprint size indicated instabilities like uncontrolled wetting. These data points are depicted in grey.

Characterisation methods

SEM, EDS and EBSD was performed in a scanning electron microscope (JEOL JSM-7200F) with a Oxford Aztec system. For SEM image, an acceleration voltage of 10 kV and a probe current of $8 \mu\text{A}$ were used. For EDS and EBSD measurements, an accelerating voltage of 15 kV accelerating voltage and a probe current of $12 \mu\text{A}$ probe current were chosen.

XPS measurements were performed on a Versaprobe IITM (Ulvac-Phi) with a X-ray induced electron imaging (SXI) system using a Al X-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.6 \text{ eV}$) operating at 15 kV and 13.2 W at an emission angle of 30° . All spectra were calibrated by the C 1s signal at a binding energy of 284.80 eV. The spectra were analyzed using CasaXPS software version 2.3.14, wherein Gaussian-Lorentzian (GL) profiles with a 70:30 ratio were employed for each component (GL (30)). A standard Shirley background was utilized for the spectra. To ensure precision, the peak area ratios and peak splitting values (Table S2) were constrained based on reference measurements^[1].

TEM lamella and APT specimens were prepared by a lift-out procedure using a focus ion beam/scanning electron microscope (FEI Helios G4 CX). TEM experiments were conducted in an aberration-corrected JEOL JEM-2200FS operating at 200 kV. The TEM images were processed using Gatan Digital Micrograph. The APT experiments were conducted in a local electrode atom probe (CAMECA LEAP 5000 XR) in laser pulsing mode at a specimen temperature of 60 K, laser energy of 50 pJ, pulse frequency of 125 kHz, detection rate of 0.3%. APT data were analyzed using IVAS 3.8.8 software.

The histograms of SECCM/EBSD image correlation, shown in Figures 2f-h were achieved by measuring the Euclidean distance within the sRGB color space between the original EBSD color and the mean color inside a 1-micron square area of a corresponding current of SECCM data. Each color bar, in Figures 2f-h, was plotted based on a color tolerance of approx. 20% of maximum color difference.

Figure S1. Six-step illustration of making a Co microelectrode (one grid of the background paper is 5 mm). The microelectrode was prepared by (a) taking a glass capillary and cutting it from the middle; (b) sealing one side of the tube with butane torch and loading a piece of cobalt wire (1.2 cm in length) into it; (c) heating the tube at a current of 17.3 A for 70 s under pumped vacuum condition; (d) after the cobalt wire is sealed in glass, loading a piece of low-melting-point (LMP) alloy and copper wire into the tube; (e) heating LMP to weld the Co and Cu parts; (f) cutting the electrode with a suitable length and putting shrinking tube on top of the Cu part.

Figure S2. (a) EBSD (IPF-Z) map of the 100-CV cycle treated electrode revealing the facet orientations present on the electrode (b) current density histogram including distributions of all facet orientations, plotted from the correlative EBSD/SECCM maps in Figure 3d,e, (c-d) correlative EBSD/SECCM maps and complete current density histogram of the as-polished Co microelectrode, plotted from the OER current density at the 2nd CV cycle (see Figure S3).

Figure S3. Correlative (a) EBSD (IPF-Z) map and (b) SECCM map of a 100-CV cycle treated electrode revealing higher OER activity of the $[02\bar{2}1]$ - (purple)-oriented facet compared to $[0001]$ -oriented Co. SECCM was performed holding a constant potential of 1 V vs. Pt. The additional correlative EBSD/SECCM measurement at a 100 CV-microelectrode, reveals that $[02\bar{2}1]$ - (purple)-oriented Co exhibits higher activity than $[0001]$ - (red)-orientated Co facets. The SECCM measurement was conducted in the hopping mode, applying a constant potential of 1 V vs. Pt QRCE to the working electrode while the tip was approached and retracted. This scanning mode was chosen to achieve higher resolution due to better droplet stability and shorter residence time. The map in Figure S4b was created from the charge by integrating the current over the time while the droplet was in contact with the electrode. Since a big part of the measured area was suspected to have suffered from either too much or insufficient wetting, only a small part of the measurement is shown here. Due to the short residence time of the droplet, no footprints could be found under SEM. The correlation of the EBSD and SECCM

maps was therefore done using optically visible features on the microelectrode which gives some uncertainty about the exact position of the plot. However, we are confident that this measurement reveals a significant difference between the $[02\bar{2}1]$ - and $[0001]$ -oriented facet.

Figure S4. CV curves recorded during SECCM at the as-polished Co microelectrode in 10 mM KOH, averaged over all 256 landings including standard deviation (error bars). The SECCM map and histogram in Figures 3h,i were generated from the current values at 0.65 V vs. Pt QRCE at the second cycle (blue star) normalized by the footprint area. The second cycle was chosen due to the lower influence of background oxidation currents before the OER onset.

Figure S5. Scanning transmission electron microscopy images of samples prepared from (a) $[0001]$ -, (b) $[02\bar{2}1]$ -, and (c) $[\bar{1}2\bar{1}0]$ - orientated Co grains, (d-f) corresponding fast-Fourier transform (FFT) images of (a-c), (g-i) inverse FFT (IFFT) by selected all the (d-e) green-color and (j-l) blue-color reflection spots in (d-f) revealing β -CoOOH and the Co matrix respectively. The superimposed IFFT images in Figure 4f were obtained by superimposing IFFT in (g-i) and (j-l).

Figure S6. Mass spectrum of APT data of Co after 100 CV samples showing the presence of O, Co, ions and OD, D₂O, Co₂O, CoO molecular ions.

Table S1: Co 2p_{3/2} spectral fitting parameters (BE.: Binding energy, L.Sh.:line shape and FWHM: full width at half-maximum)

Peaks	Peaks	BE.(eV)	FWHM	L.Sh.	Area	%Area
Co ^{III} OOH	1	779.96	1.73	GL(30)	756.53	55.59
	2	781.28	1.73	GL(30)	295.05	21.68
	3	782.96	1.73	GL(30)	60.52	4.45
	4	786.96	4	GL(30)	105.91	7.78
Co ^{II} (OH) ₂	1	780.52	0.74	GL(30)	55.97	4.11
	2	782.32	2.5	GL(30)	38.62	2.84
	3	786.11	4.4	GL(30)	44.77	3.29
	4	790.61	1.63	GL(30)	3.53	0.26

Table S2: Percentage of total area and binding energy (eV) components of the multiplet pattern for the Co 2p_{3/2} in Co^{III}OOH and Co^{II}(OH)₂.

Compound	Peak 1	%	Peak 2	%	Peak 3	%	Peak 4	%
Co ^{II} (OH) ₂	780.4	38.1	782.2	26.6	786	33	790.4	2.4
Co ^{III} OOH	780.1	61.4	781.4	24.5	783.1	5.2	790.1	8.9

References

- [1] M. C. Biesinger, B. P. Payne, A. P. Grosvenor, L. W. Lau, A. R. Gerson, R. S. C. Smart, *Applied Surface Science* **2011**, 257, 2717-2730.